

DESIGN SCIENCE RESEARCH FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF A UNIVERSITY COURSE ON THE INFORMED USE OF SEARCH ENGINES

M. Platz, Saarland University, Saarbrücken, Germany

Abstract

From primary school age at the latest, children need the skills to search for information correctly, evaluate search results, and assess the potential risks of disclosing personal data in school and everyday life. In this paper, the question of how primary school teacher trainees can be prepared to incorporate the topic of search engines into their lessons is addressed. Design Science Research is applied, and the course structure and design principles are presented. The course intends to give the students confidence in dealing with and the relevance of the informed use of search engines in primary education to increase the probability that they include the topic in their future teaching. However, no statement can yet be made about the seminar’s influence on future teacher behavior.

THE INFORMED USE OF SEARCH ENGINES

Search engines are essential for participation in (not only digital) life. However, the lack of transparency of algorithms for filtering information, user profiling, and the design of the user interfaces of popular platforms are leading to increasing immaturity in user behavior and a low level of risk awareness regarding privacy. Many of these effects are amplified by AI chatbots.

The KIM-Study 2022 [1], a basic study on media use by 6 to 13-year-olds, showed that 70% of children use the Internet. At the same time, it demonstrates that more and more children are using media independently and without adult supervision [1]. Concerning the miniKIM study 2020 [2], Textor [3] emphasizes that even 2 to 5-year-olds’ leisure time is already intensively characterized using media (devices). Even primary school children use search engines like Google [4; 5] without knowing or questioning how

they work: “The simplicity and clean interface of Google conceal a complexity that is not understood by users” [6, p. 4]. This applies not only to children and young people but also to adults.

To promote an informed use of search engines, search engine literacy must be promoted among users to promote search and information literacy. Search engine literacy is an aspect of search literacy, which is an aspect of information literacy. Information literacy refers to the ability to understand that information is needed, to search for it effectively and efficiently, to evaluate it appropriately, and to use it. It also includes integrating new information into previous knowledge and utilizing it legally, economically, socially, and ethically to achieve goals [7]. Search literacy refers directly to obtaining information and describes the ability to find and access the desired information to satisfy information needs efficiently and effectively [7]. Developing search engine literacy means gaining knowledge about the basic functioning of search engines (such as ranking, filtering, and sorting algorithms) and the following aspects: findability, linguistic functions and query language [7; 8].

In this context, the overarching research question of the project is: How can a sensible use of search engines be promoted? The following subordinate research questions, among others, will be analyzed:

- (RQ1) How can teaching-learning arrangements be developed to promote the informed use of search engines?
- (RQ2) How can primary school teacher trainees be prepared to incorporate the topic of search engines into their lessons?
- (RQ3) How should information materials be designed to promote an informed approach to search engines?

Figure 1: Process, status, and planning of the project.

Fig. 1 shows the process, the status, and the further planning of the project. Design Science Research (see next section) will be used to answer the research questions. The results of the three sub-projects (Fig. 1) influence each other. RQ2 is addressed in this paper. To this end, the current draft of a seminar concept is described, intended to enable student teachers to develop teaching-learning arrangements for the informed use of search engines.

DESIGN SCIENCE RESEARCH

Design Science Research (DSR) is a paradigm rooted in the philosophy of pragmatism. It has its foundations in the sciences and the construction of the artificial ('The Sciences of the Artificial' [9], first edition 1970). DSR involves problem-solving research to answer research questions about human problems, producing useful artifacts [10], e.g., models, concepts, instantiations, and methods [11].

There are many different DSR models that have been developed and are used in various disciplines. In this paper,

models from the fields of 'education' and 'information systems' are used to visualize synergy effects and derive suitable models for the research described.

What the models in the field of 'education' all have in common is the emphasis on cycles or iterations [12, p. 59]. The terminology used to describe the different phases within such cycles varies. What seems to be consistent across design research projects are the following phases (or work areas, cf. [13]) of each so-called macrocycle of design research ([12, p. 59], cf. also [14, p. 35]): (1) preparation and design, (2) implementation and (3) analysis and re-design. These can also be found in the models from the field of 'information systems' (e.g. [15]).

The 'Four Cycle View of Design Science Research' [10, p. 5] is applied in this project (see Fig. 2). It is described below, linked to didactic development research, and guiding questions for the different cycles are formulated based on [10; 13; 16; 17] to support researchers in the implementation of DSR projects.

Figure 2: The Four-Cycle View [10] (adapted by the author of this paper).

The Four Cycle View [10] (see Fig. 2) is an extension of the Three Cycle View [16]: “The Relevance Cycle bridges the contextual environment of the research project with the design science activities. The Rigor Cycle connects the design science activities with the knowledge base of scientific foundations, experience, and expertise that informs the research project. The central Design Cycle iterates between the core activities of building and evaluating the design artifacts and processes of the research. I posit that these three cycles must be present and clearly identifiable in a design science research project.” [16, p. 88]. The fourth cycle was implemented to better capture the dynamic nature of artifact design for dynamic real-world contexts. It encompasses the impact of design artifacts on their broader organizational and social context [10].

Relevance Cycle

“Good design science research often begins by identifying and representing opportunities and problems in an

actual application environment.” [16, p. 89]. The Relevance Cycle initiates the DSR with an application context that not only provides the requirements for the research (e.g., the issue/problem to be addressed) as input but also defines acceptance criteria for the final evaluation of the research results. The design research results must be fed back into the environment for investigation and application in the environment. Field trials can be used to determine whether further iterations of the cycle are required in the research project [16].

Table 1: Relevance Cycle - Guiding Questions

1 How can the problem space for the DSR project be defined and visualized?

2 What does the solution space look like? (Delimitation of the research project; [17]). The following central questions from the work area specifying and structuring learning objects [13] can help determine the solution space:

- What is to be learned first, and with what focus?
- What educational content should be emphasized when formulating the topics?
- How exactly must the learning object be constructed to enable adequate mediation between subject-specific and individual perspectives?
- What is to be learned first, and with what focus?

3 Does the design artifact improve the environment, and how can this improvement be measured?

- Through which contexts, views or perspectives can contexts, views or perspectives be used to find links to the learners' previous experiences that promote learning?
- In what way might the learning object itself need to be changed or restructured so that it can be learned?
- Which sequencing into sub-subjects enables learning paths according to which design principles that are accessible to many learners? [13]

Rigor Cycle

Design science relies on an extensive knowledge base of scientific theories and methods that form the foundation for rigorous design research. Equally important, the knowledge base contains two types of additional knowledge: The experience and expertise that defines the current state of the field of application of the research and the pre-existing artifacts and processes (or meta-artifacts) found in the field of application. The Rigor Cycle provides the research project with pre-existing knowledge to ensure its innovation. Researchers must thoroughly research and reference the knowledge base to ensure that the designs produced are research contributions and not routine designs based on the application of known processes [16].

Table 2: Rigor Cycle - Guiding Questions

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|---|
| 1 Are the drafts created research contributions and not just routine drafts? |
| 2 Which extensions of the original theories and methods were made during the research, which new meta-artifacts (design products and processes), and which experiences were gained during the implementation of the research and the testing of the artifact in the application environment? |

- How can the local teaching-learning theory be modified, further differentiated, and increasingly empirically validated based on the results of the design experiments? [13]

Design Cycle

“The internal design cycle is the heart of any design science research project.” [16, p. 90]. The design cycle moves more quickly between the construction of an artifact, its evaluation, and the subsequent feedback for further design refinement. Simon [9] describes the nature of this cycle as generating design alternatives and evaluating (Rigor Cycle) the other options against the requirements (Relevance Cycle) until a satisfactory design is achieved. During the execution of the design cycle, it is essential to balance the design effort and the evaluation of the evolving design artifact [16].

Table 3: Design Cycle - Guiding Questions

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|---|
| 1 Which DSR process model fits the research? |
| 2 How can the research processes used in the project be documented and justified? |
| 3 How can the design artifacts be (further) developed? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which learning activities should be initiated according to which design principles and tasks for which objectives? • Which teaching and learning materials can be used to support the processes? • How can typical hurdles on the pupils' learning paths be avoided or overcome? [13] |
| 4 How can the developed artifact be evaluated? |

Change and Impact Cycle

The goals of many DSR projects are typically driven by factors in the external environment in which the designed artifacts are to be embedded. From a dynamic perspective, the Change and Impact Cycle allows researchers to become more aware of the dynamics in the broader organizational or societal context and to understand and manage these dynamics within the context of a research project. Today's organizations and societies are constantly changing. Such external dynamics highlight that the aims, rationale, and requirements for DSR projects can change throughout a research project. A particular change in the broader context may also create a problem that did not previously exist (or was perceived) and thus be the trigger for the entire DSR project. The introduction of the artifact into its immediate context of use may, in turn, also lead to changes in the broader environment, resulting in new or changed requirements for the artifact and thus new subsequent iterations through the cycles or, in the worst case, even making the artifact no longer usable [10].

Table 4: Change and Impact Cycle

1 What organizational, environmental, and social changes could influence the DSR project?

2 What artifact side effects and long-term effects could arise?

In the next section, a university course that is developed with DSR addressing search engines is described.

THE COURSE

The course ‘Computer Science Education in Primary School’ is anchored in the curriculum as a mandatory course for primary school teacher students at Saarland University (Germany) since 2021 [18]. It is assigned to mathematics. The learning objectives are to acquire basic knowledge in the field of computer science education in the use of digital media for mathematical teaching and learning processes in primary school and to determine mathematics didactically meaningful applications of digital media, create didactic concepts, and reflect on them critically. The topics addressed in the course are contents of computer science education at the primary level from a mathematics didactics perspective (e.g., algorithms (coding); languages & automata (robots & co.); computer science, people, and society (cryptology)), the design of teaching-learning arrangements with the use of digital media and its use in teaching practice. A unique feature of the course is its practical relevance: The developed teaching-learning arrangement is implemented as part of a teaching experiment in the school internship of the students, and afterwards, they analyze and reflect on the experiment.

Search Engines are chosen as a topic for this course because many areas of computer science are used to ensure the functionality of the search engine, and most of them can be made tangible through CS Unplugged [27] and linked to the competences for computer science education in primary education formulated by the Society for Computer Science Germany [19], e.g.:

- **Algorithms** – How do you make a search engine scalable? And why are search engines so fast? (Search Algorithms, Sorting Algorithms, Graphs, Search Index, etc.)
- **Languages and automata** – How do you communicate with a search engine? (Search Literacy) How to provide a user-friendly GUI? (Human-Computer-Interaction)
- **Information and Data** – Computer security and encryption: How do we protect the user?
- **Computer science, people, and society** – What opportunities and risks does using a search engine have? (Ranking, Filter Bubbles, Privacy, AI)

To develop coherent teaching-learning arrangements to promote the informed use of search engines, several aspects must be considered: According to the Conference of Education Ministers’ (KMK) strategy [20], developing and acquiring the necessary skills for life in a digital world goes far beyond basic computer skills and affects all subjects. They can, therefore, not be assigned to an isolated learning area (p. 12). In the strategy, the KMK formulates competencies for the development of which each subject with its

specific approaches to the digital world should contribute. Consequently, concepts that can be implemented in regular primary school lessons in combination with traditional teaching topics without taking up additional teaching time must be developed [21]. In the basic curriculum Media education and computer education [22] of the Saarland, which is based on the KMK strategy paper [20], in the competence area ‘problem solving and modeling’, in addition to developing problem-solving strategies with the help of algorithms, particular emphasis is also placed on reflecting on the influences of algorithms and the impact of the automation of processes in the digital world [22, p. 6]. Teaching concepts for promoting the informed use of search engines can be connected here. The subject-specific and didactic reference links to the traditional content of subject teaching – in this case, maths – the reference to computer science education and the topic of search engines and, finally, reflection to conclude dealing with search engines.

In the first two course cycles (winter semester 2021/22 and summer semester 2022), it was observed that the trainee teachers developed teaching units in which search engines were addressed but not linked to the content of regular lessons, or conversely, that the subject was linked to computer science education, but the search engine context was not addressed. Only the use of the search engine was addressed so that it remains a ‘black box’ and, e.g., the algorithms for filtering remain invisible [23]. Hevner and vom Brocke [17] note that it cannot be assumed that students have comprehensive knowledge of research processes and methods and that many also lack practical experience with real problems in the workplace. They, therefore, recommend involving students in practical projects where they can apply what they have learned. The seminar aims to develop teaching-learning arrangements to promote the informed use of search engines, involving them in the overarching research project (see Fig. 1). Through practical experience and reflection on their teaching activities as well as acting as DSR researchers, students should acquire specialized, didactic, and practical knowledge and a sense of confidence in dealing with and the relevance of the informed use of search engines in primary education.

Although the iterative nature of design science research is emphasized, this does not mean that design researchers must always repeat macrocycles; so-called microcycles can also be used [12; 24; 25; 26]. Microcycles occur within a design experiment as researchers attempt to adapt both the instructional activities and their underlying theory. Each microcycle consists of an anticipatory thought experiment, the execution of teaching activities, and the analysis that leads to the adaptation or revision of subsequent activities. In practice, design research can vary in how much it builds on either microcycles, macrocycles, or both [24, p. 879]. To guide the students, they go through a DSR microcycle with support and focus mainly on Relevance Cycle – Question 2 (Table 1) and Design Cycle – Questions 3 & 4 (Table 3).

The following design principles were used to re-design the course: If you want to design a course for teacher training students on the development of teaching-learning

arrangements to promote the informed use of search engines, then you are best advised to:

- Include course elements to create Awareness of and concern for the risks of internet searches (Table 5, session 2).
- Give the students an already developed teaching-learning arrangement that they can optimize (e.g., those from CS Unplugged [27]; sessions 3, 4, and 7).
- Provide the (prospective) teachers with a model to support them in lesson planning. One crucial part is the theoretically sound understanding of a concept (originally on the topic of ‘algorithms’ [28] transferred to ‘search engines’ and expanded to include a reflection [29] (sessions 5 and 6).
- Let the students become active participants in and designers of the course (sessions 8 to 15).

Table 5 provides an overview of the course structure.

Table 5: Course Structure

Ses- sion	Topic	Mainly ad- dressed cycle
1	Organizational matters & in- troduction: Computer Science Education in Primary School	Relevance Cycle
2	Search better and safer on the Internet	Relevance Cycle
3	CS Unplugged	Rigor Cycle
4	Search Engines in Mathemat- ics Education	Rigor Cycle
5, 6	Teaching-Learning-Arrange- ments in Mathematics in Pri- mary School	Rigor Cycle
7	Analysis of existing Teaching- Learning-Arrangements to pro- mote the informed use of search engines	Rigor Cycle
8, 9, 10, 11	Development of teaching- learning arrangements to pro- mote the informed use of search engines as further de- velopment of CS Unplugged units	Design Cycle
12, 13, 14	Testing with the course partici- pants and further development	Design Cycle
15	Reflection & Conclusion, Term Paper & Wikiversity	Rigor Cycle

Practical experience and reflection on one’s teaching activities, as well as acting as a DSR researcher, are intended to impart specialized didactic and practical knowledge and a sense of security in dealing with search engines at the primary level.

In the course evaluations (as part of the SaLUt II project at Saarland University, part of the quality offensive Teacher training program funded by the BMBF), the students rated the course very positively. This is reflected in the above-

average scores on the scales of satisfaction, event quality, lecturers, usefulness, and relevance.

A more detailed evaluation can be done through the reflection the students sent to the docent after their trial in the school intern. However, no statement can yet be made about the seminar’s influence on future teacher behavior. For this, the participants would have to be interviewed again much later, when they have completed their studies and are working as teachers.

CONCLUSIONS

To assess the current state of DSR presented in this paper, guidelines to clarify the requirements for effective design science research and to be able to evaluate DSR projects are taken from the fields of ‘information systems’ [30] and ‘education’ [31] (Table 6).

Table 6: Guidelines for the evaluation of DSR projects

1 Design as an Artifact/ Consistency (construct validity)/ Practicality – Expected: The artifact ‘concept of the seminar computer science education in primary school’ is a method (March & Smith, 1995), i.e., a series of steps to counter the difficulties of integrating the informed use of search engines into the primary classroom.
2 Problem Relevance/ Relevance (content validity)/ Practicality – Actual/ Effectiveness – Ex- pected: The relevance of integrating the informed use of search engines into primary school lessons was described in the first section. Scientific find- ings were used to design the artifact. The seminar concept can be employed in the primary school teaching degree program, and it is hoped that the students can be given a sense of confidence in deal- ing with and feel the relevance of dealing with search engines in primary education so that they can integrate it into their future teaching.
3 Design Evaluation/ Effectiveness – Actual: The usefulness, quality, and effectiveness of the artifact were checked, among other things, by the student contributions in the term paper and by teaching evaluations. On this basis, changes were made to the seminar concept. However, whether the semi- nar impacts the students’ future teaching behavior has not yet been investigated.
4 Research Contributions: This paper presents the seminar concept of computer science education in primary school, which other universities can adopt (in whole or in part) (possibly in an adapted form).

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- 5 Research Rigor:** To assess the artifact, the student contributions in the term paper were evaluated, and teaching evaluations were considered. Within the framework of the macrocycle, qualitative evaluation methods will also be used, and a possibility of the actual effects on the students' subsequent teaching behavior is to be developed. (For the construction of the artifact, see guideline 2).
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- 6 Design as a Search Process:** The teaching-learning arrangements are developed so that they can be used directly in school. The students publish their developments in a fact sheet format [32] as OER at Wikiversity: https://de.wikiversity.org/wiki/Open-Source4School/Lernumgebungen_zur_Informatischen_Bildung_im_Mathematikunterricht_der_Primarstufe#Search_Engine_Literacy
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- 7 Communication of Research:** This paper shares the seminar concept with a scientific audience. Challenges were presented in [23].
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REFERENCES

- [1] KIM (2022). *Kindheit, Medien, Internet*. Mpfs.
- [2] miniKIM (2020). *Kleinkinder und Medien*. Mpfs.
- [3] Textor, M.R.: Mediennutzung von Kleinkindern: die miniKIM-Studie 2020. *Das Kita-Handbuch, 2021*.
- [4] JIM (2018). *Jugend, Information, Medien*. Mpfs.
- [5] Feil, Ch., Gieger, Ch., & Grobbing, A. (2013). *Projekt: Informationsverhalten von Kindern im Internet – eine empirische Studie zur Nutzung von Suchmaschinen*. Deutsches Jugendinstitut.
- [6] Le Deuff, O. (2017). Search engine literacy. In *European Conference on Information Literacy* (pp. 359–365). Springer.
- [7] Karatassis, I. (2015). A gamification framework for enhancing search literacy. In *FDIA 2015*, 6 (pp. 3–6).
- [8] Fuhr, N. (2014). *Internet search engines – Lecture script for the course in SS 2014*. http://www.is.inf.uni-due.de/courses/ir_ss14/ISMs_1-7.pdf
- [9] Simon, H. A. (1996). *The sciences of the artificial*. MIT Press.
- [10] Drechsler, A., & Hevner, A. (2016). A four-cycle model of IS design science research: capturing the dynamic nature of IS artifact design. *DESRIST 2016*.
- [11] March, S. T., & Smith, G. F. (1995). Design and natural science research on information technology. *Decision support systems, 15*(4), 251–266.
- [12] Bakker, A. (2018). *Design research in education: A practical guide for early career researchers*. Routledge.
- [13] Prediger, S., Link, M., Hinz, R.; Hußmann, S., Thiele, J., Ralle, B. (2012). Lehr-Lernprozesse initiieren und erforschen – Fachdidaktische Entwicklungsforschung im Dortmund-Modell. *MNU 65*(8), 452–457.
- [14] Gravemeijer, K., & Prediger, S. (2019). Topic-specific design research: An introduction. In G. Kaiser & N. Presmeg (Eds.), *Compendium for early career researchers in mathematics education* (S. 33–57). Springer.
- [15] Peffers, K., Tuunanen, T., Rothenberger, M. A., & Chatterjee, S. (2007). A design science research methodology for information systems research. *Journal of Management Information Systems, 24*(3), 45–77.
- [16] Hevner, A. R. (2007). A three cycle view of design science research. *Scandinavian journal of information systems, 19*(2), 87–92.
- [17] Hevner, A. R., & vom Brocke, J. (2023). A Proficiency Model for Design Science Research Education. *Journal of Information Systems Education, 34*(3), 264–278.
- [18] UdS, (2021). *Modulhandbuch der Studienfächer und der Profildächer im Studiengang Lehramt für die Primarstufe*.
- [19] GI (2019). *Kompetenzen für informatische Bildung im Primarbereich*. Empfehlungen der Gesellschaft für Informatik e.V.
- [20] KMK (2016). *Strategie der Kultusministerkonferenz „Bildung in der digitalen Welt“* (Beschluss der Kultusministerkonferenz vom 08.12.2016)
- [21] Platz, M., Müller, L., Niehaus, E. & Müller, S. (2021). Modules for Open Search in Mathematics Teaching. In *Proceedings of 3rd OSSYM*, CERN.
- [22] MBK (2019). *Basiscurriculum Medienbildung und informatische Bildung*. Ministerium für Bildung und Kultur Saarland.
- [23] Platz, M. (2022). Search Engine Literacy – mehr als Kompetenzen zum Recherchieren mit Suchmaschinen. In T. Irion, M. Peschel & D. Schmeinck (Eds.), *Grundschule und Digitalität. Beiträge zur Reform der Grundschule 155* (S. 298–307). Grundschulverband.
- [24] Prediger, S., Gravemeijer, K. & Confrey, J. (2015). Design research with a focus on learning processes: An overview on achievements and challenges. *ZDM, 47*, 877–891.
- [25] Gravemeijer, K., & Cobb, P. (2006). Design research from a learning design perspective. In J. van den Akker, K. Gravemeijer, S. McKenney, & N. Nieveen (Eds.), *Educational DesignResearch: The design, development and evaluation of programs, processes and products* (S. 17–51). Routledge.
- [26] Cobb, P., McClain, K., & Gravemeijer, K. (2003). Learning about statistical covariation. *Cognition and instruction, 21*(1), 1–78.
- [27] CS Unplugged (n.d.). *Topics*. <https://www.csunplugged.org/en/topics/>
- [28] Etzold, H., Noack, S. & Jurk, A. (2019). *Algorithmen im Alltag. Leitfaden für Lehrerinnen und Lehrer. Teil 1: Hintergrund und Theorie*. Digitales Lernen Grundschule, Universität Potsdam.
- [29] Platz, M., Klan, F. & Decker, A. (2022). Developing and promoting search engine literacy in primary education. In *Proceedings of 4th OSSYM*, CERN.
- [30] Hevner, A. R., March, S. T., Park, J., & Ram, S. (2004). Design science in information systems research. *Management Information Systems Quarterly, 28*(1), 75–105.
- [31] Plomp, T. (2013). Educational design research: An introduction. T. Plomp & N. Nieveen (Eds.), *Educational design research* (pp. 11–50). SLO.
- [32] Platz, M. (2020). Ein Schema zur kriteriengeleiteten Erstellung und Dokumentation von Lernumgebungen mit Einsatz digitaler Medien. In F. Dilling & F. Pielsticker (Eds.), *Mathematische Lehr-Lernprozesse im Kontext digitaler Medien* (S. 29–56). Springer.